

Energy performance certificates under discussion

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ABSTRACT

After 10 years of track record, the current Energy Performance Certification (EPC) schemes across the EU face several challenges which have led to not fully accomplish their initial objectives: lack of accuracy, a gap between theoretical and real consumption patterns, absence of proper protocols for inclusion of smart and novel technologies, little convergence across EU schemes, lack of trust in the market and very little user awareness related to energy efficiency.

In the context of ePANACEA, an EU-funded project which aims to create a holistic energy performance assessment for the next generation of energy performance certification methods, participatory actions have been included in order to understand the needs and expectations from stakeholders target groups (especially end-users and policy makers).

This communication presents the results of this fluent dialog obtained from end-users workshops and stakeholder interviews held in six EU countries and five Regional Exploitation Boards covering nearly all EU member states

Keywords: energy performance certificates (EPCs), stakeholder EPC-related perception analysis, EPC-related energy policy recommendations.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) was born as an information tool for building owners, occupiers and real estate actors regarding the energy efficiency of a building, and nowadays it is a key policy instrument for the decarbonisation of the EU building stock. It was first introduced by the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD, 2002/31/EC) [1]. The following EPBD recast (2010/91/EU) [2] and amendment (2018/844/EU) [3] put forward additional provisions to strengthen and enhance the quality of the EPC in the Member States (MSs).

But after more than 10 years of track record, the current Energy Performance Certification (EPC) schemes face several challenges which have led to not fully accomplish their initial objectives: lack of accuracy, a gap between theoretical and real consumption patterns, absence of proper protocols for inclusion of smart and novel technologies, little convergence across EU schemes, lack of trust in the market and very little user awareness related to energy efficiency.

Most MSs had to develop and implement their own EPC scheme from scratch, following the general methodology included in the EPBD, so rather different approaches can be found across EU. But in general, all EPCs face the same challenges in different degrees of intensity.

On the other hand, the new provisions included in the current revision of the EPBD [4] intend to ensure the comparability and reliability of EPCs across the Union and link it with other indicators (such as indoor air quality or smart readiness indicator) and databases and instruments (such as building passports and building logbook), etc.

In this context the objective of the **ePANACEA Horizon2020 project** [5] is to develop a holistic methodology for energy performance assessment and certification of buildings that can overcome the above-mentioned challenges. The vision of ePANACEA is to become a relevant instrument in the European energy transition through the building sector. ePANACEA comprises the creation of a prototype (the Smart Energy Performance Assessment Platform) making use of the most advanced techniques in dynamic and automated simulation modelling, big data analysis and machine learning, inverse modelling or the estimation of potential energy savings and economic viability check.

For that purpose, understanding the different needs and expectations of the end-users, policy makers and other stakeholders with regard to the EPC in all EU countries is an important part of ePANACEA project. The ePANACEA methodology involves stakeholders from the beginning and establishes a continuous feedback loop until the end of the three year project duration (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Feedback loops to the methodology development

As part of the participatory actions, the acceptance of the ePANACEA approach will be tested and validated in order to become aligned with and meet the needs of national public bodies, end-users and other stakeholders.

Another output obtained from this continuous dialog is to provide policy recommendations regarding the next generation of EPCs.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. General concept. Definition of participatory actions

The dialog with European policy makers, certification bodies, end-users and other stakeholders have been organized through two main types of participatory actions:

- **Users workshops:** Three rounds of five end-user workshops have been set up during the project lifetime in the five ePANACEA pilot countries (AT- Austria, BE- Belgium (Flemish region), EL- Greece, ES- Spain, FI- Finland). In addition, the first user-workshop was conducted in DE- Germany.

Users workshops are addressed in the first place to end-users of EPCs (building occupants, owners and tenants-, building managers), and in the second place to other stakeholders who get in contact with end users and are expected to influence end users' perception, (e.g. energy advisors, architects, multipliers of EPC like real estate companies, housing associations, landlords). Including them in the study helps to understand end users' decision making and behaviour regarding the use of EPCs and the uptake of energy efficiency measures.

Supporting the first round of workshops, a set of semi-structural individual interviews was carried out previously. The interviews (conducted with end-users and other stakeholders) were scheduled in the five pilot countries (AT, BE, EL, ES, FI) + DE.

• **Regional Exploitation Boards (REBs):** Five REBs covering nearly all member states (EU-28+Norway) have been planned to meet three times during the project lifetime. REBs involve representatives from all stakeholders identified as important, including but not limited to, policy makers and certification bodies, building products manufacture associations, associations of energy experts/auditors, other professional associations, consumer associations, etc.

Figure 2 shows the structure of these five groups based on geographical and climatic criteria, country population, EPC method variety and national renovation rates.

REBs are led by project partners* (Northern REB: VTT; Western REB: VITO; Central REB: EAST; Southwestern REB: CENER; Southeastern REB: CRES). They also include project partners involved in the testing and demonstration boards to guarantee the validation test conclusions transfer.

* VTT: Technical Research Centre of Finland; VITO: Flemish Institute for Technological Research; EAST: Energy Agency of Styria; TUW: Vienna University of Technology; CENER: National Renewable Energy Centre of Spain; IDAE: Institute for the Diversification and Energy Saving; CRES: Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving of Greece.

Figure 2. Overview on the REB structure

This research study is based on the analysis of the stakeholder's needs, their insights and their EPC-related perception obtained from the 1st and 2nd round of users workshops and REB meetings. The 1st round of users' workshops and REB meetings were organized from Nov 2020 to Jan 2021 whereas the 2nd round of users workshops and REB meetings took place from Nov 2021 to Jan 2022, all of them in online format due to the COVID-19 outbreak.

2.2. Users workshops approach

Previous user interviews

As a preparatory task, a set of end-users and stakeholder interviews was conducted in the five pilot

countries (AT, BE, EL, ES, FI) and DE before organizing the 1st round of workshops. The purpose was to have a first insight into end-user's knowledge, perception, interests and needs regarding EPC with the idea of better organizing subsequent workshops, in which user-needs would be further investigated.

In total 63 interviews were conducted on the phone or online in national languages, with the support of ePANACEA national partners, of which 38 were interviews with end-users and 25 with other stakeholders.

Users workshops

The same structure, the power point presentations and the same questionnaires, translated to the national languages, were prepared for each set of workshops (6 in the 1st round, 5 in the 2nd round) with a possibility of adaptation to local conditions by ePANACEA national partners.

The two-hour workshops were conducted in the national languages and included an introductory part regarding the ePANACEA project, an on-line questionnaire to be filled out by the end-users, a discussion session with participants and a conclusion section.

The following topics for discussion were proposed:

- 1st workshops round: "user's needs workshop"

The objective was to explore participants' needs and interests regarding the EPC. Firstly, a set of potential suggestions the country-specific EPC was presented to ensure that all participants had understood the main information. Critiques and needs regarding were collected in a mind map included in the ePANACEA report [6]. During the second part of the workshop, some suggestions to improve features of the EPC were presented to be discussed in the plenary and partly evaluated in Google Forms by participants. The proposed suggestions were based on a previous literatura review, the user interviews and some insights from the ePANACEA report [7]. Questions in Google Forms covered participants' understanding and perceived usefulness of the presented suggestions which influence the intention to use EPCs.

- 2nd workshops round: "1st acceptance test of EPC"

The purpose was to test users' acceptance of the ePANACEA proposal for a new EPC oriented towards end-users and collect suggestions for improvement. The idea of a new end-users-oriented EPC was born during the past interviews and 1st round of workshops.

Features of existing EPC schemes (e.g. energy label, main performance indicators, partial and additional indicators, recommendations, format of EPC etc.), variables influencing technology acceptance (e.g. perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, behavioural intention to use, main interests and preferences etc.) and proposals for a new end-user-oriented EPC (e.g. main performance indicators, illustrations of the energy label, partial performance indicators etc.) were evaluated. A mix of question types was presented via Polleverywhere to collect and display consolidated answers to the participants immediately. In addition to that, open discussions helped understand 'why' participants selected a certain answer (or not) and to gather suggestions on how to improve the presented illustrations. [8]

**NOTE: A "2nd acceptance test of EPC" is proposed in the 3rd round of workshops, not included in this communication.*

In total, 11 end-user workshops were held in six EU countries: six in the 1st round with 63 participants, and five in the 2nd round with 102 participants. The following Figure 3 gives an overview of the workshop participant composition. Just over 50% were only end-users.

Participatory action	Date	n° participants	Language
1st Be-Flemish end-users workshop	17/12/2020	6 (2 other stakeh.)	Flemish
1st Spanish end-users workshop	13/01/2021	16 (8 other stakeh.)	Spanish
1st Austrian end-users workshop	14/01/2021	14 (11 other stakeh.)	German
1st Greek end-users workshop	13/01/2021	13 (5 other stakeh.)	Greek
1st Finland end-users workshop	13/01/2021	6 (3 other stakeh.)	English
1st German end-users workshop	17/12/2020	8 (5 other stakeh.)	German
Total- 1st round workshops		63 (34 other stakeh.)	
2nd Be-Flemish end-users workshop	18/01/2022	21 (13 other stakeh.)	Flemish
2nd Spanish end-users workshop	18/01/2022	27 (13 other stakeh.)	Spanish
2nd Austrian end-users workshop	25/01/2022	26 (13 other stakeh.)	German
2nd Greek end-users workshop	18/01/2022	18 (3 other stakeh.)	Greek
2nd Finland end-users workshop	14/01/2022	10 (6 other stakeh.)	English
Total- 2nd round workshops		102 (48 other stakeh.)	

Figure 3. Overview on participants' structure among the users workshops.

2.3. Regional Exploitation Boards meetings approach

The two first rounds of meetings were prepared based on the material developed within ePANACEA project activities. These documents are available at the ePANACEA webpage and at Zenodo open digital repository ([6] [7], [9], [10]).

The same structure, power point presentations, and the same material for interactive discussions were prepared for each set of meetings (5 meetings per round) with a possibility of adaptation to local conditions by REB leaders. The two-hour meetings included an introductory part regarding the ePANACEA project, two/three discussion sessions which were split into presentations and interactive parts, and a conclusion section and next steps. The MURAL interactive whiteboard tool was chosen to collect the stakeholder's responds. It allowed answering simple questions with "post-its".

The following topics for discussion were proposed:

1st meetings round:

- 1) Inclusion of smart and novel technologies in the future EPCs.
- 2) New innovative features to include in the EPCs.
- 3) Increase of user-friendliness and understanding of EPC through new report layout.

2nd meetings round:

- 1) Insights and recommendations from end-user interviews and workshops from 6 EU countries.
- 2) Convergence and prioritisation of key indicators for EPC's.

In total, 10 meetings were held where 48 highly relevant institutions from 23 countries participated in the 1st round) whereas 39 institutions from 20 different countries discussed the different topics proposed in the 2nd round. A list of participating organisations can be found in ePANACEA REB section website [11]. The following Figure 4 gives an overview of the participants of the two first meeting rounds of the five REBs and their structure. Nearly 40% are policy makers and certification bodies, followed by EPC experts (29%) and different professional associations (14%).

Participatory action	Date	Participating institutions	Countries
1st Western REB meeting	27.10.2020	6 (2 PPs)	4 BG, IE, UK, AT
1st Southwestern REB meeting	30.11.2020	12 (4 PPs)	4 ES, IT, MT, AT
1st Central REB meeting	01.12.2020	12 (2 PPs)	7 AT, CZ, PO, HU, SK, SI, DE
1st Southeastern REB meeting	03.12.2020	12 (2 PPs)	5 GR, CY, BG, RO, AT
1st Northern REB meeting	09.12.2020	6 (1 PPs)	4 FI, EE, LV, NO
Total - 1st round of REB meetings		48	23 different
2nd Western REB meeting	08.12.2021	4 (1 PPs)	3 BG, IE, UK
2nd Southwestern REB	13.12.2021	10 (3 PPs)	5 ES, IT, MT, PT, AT
2nd Central REB meeting	01.12.2021	10 (2 PPs)	6 AT, CZ, PO, HU, SK, SI, DE
2nd Southeastern REB	13.12.2021	8 (1 PPs)	3 GR, BG, RO
2nd Northern REB meeting	29.11.2021	7 (2 PPs)	5 FI, EE, LV, NO
Total- 2nd round of REB meetings		39	20 different

Figure 4. Overview on participants' structure among the five REB meetings

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section includes part of the total findings obtained from the participatory action analysis, those especially focused on the specific stakeholders' needs and expectations towards the future EPCs.

3.1. New innovative features

With the purpose of improving accuracy to instil trust in the market, and to improve the end-user acceptance and the EPC usefulness, 9 relevant features (see Figure 5) were discussed and assessed in the three out of the five REBs.

TRUST IMPROVEMENT of end users	ACCURACY IMPROVEMENT of calculation results
Use of actual consumption data and energy costs (energy bills) as additional information and for benchmarking	Use of measurement data
Use of actual operational conditions	Dynamic building simulation
Fixed reference value for energy performance rating (e.g. fixed values per building class...)	Calibration of building simulation (static, dynamic) with measurement data
Variable reference value for energy performance rating (e.g. comparison with reference building)	Use of actual operational conditions
Mandatory on site visit	Mandatory on site visit
Tailored recommendations for user behaviour, nZEB renovation, etc.	

Figure 5. Overview on discussed features during the REB meetings

Figure 6. Overview on discussed features during the REB meetings

According to the REB feedback (see Figure 6 and [12]), the highest potential for **trust improvement** and already mandatory in some EPC schemes is assigned to **resilient tailored recommendations**. Well prepared recommendations have a high added value for end users, but it may be difficult for them to identify the quality of the recommendations. **Mandatory on-site visits** as well as **use of actual consumption data** could also increase trust, but the framework conditions of consumption data (measurement period, operational conditions, users...) need to be given as well, however it makes comparability more complicated for non-experts.

The highest contribution to **increase accuracy** of national EPCs is seen for the feature of **dynamic building simulation**. It is already mandatory in Estonia (except SFH) and it works out well.

To completely base national EPC schemes on **measurement data and actual operational conditions** is widely perceived as not applicable and with low implementation feasibility because the introduction of **the user behaviour complicates the comparability of different buildings**.

In addition, using **more complex models and calculation methodologies** would **increase costs** for issuing EPCs and expert knowledge from EPC issuers is necessary. Some countries mentioned that the current EPC calculation methodology is already very complex and additional requirements may overstrain EPC issuers. For this reason, a **good education** of EPC issuers is without alternative.

3.2. Analysis of user needs and expectations towards future EPCs

3.2.1. User perceptions and needs

The 1st round of user workshops+ interviews showed that end-users know little about the EPC. They perceive it as a mandatory document which they use for contractual actions such as deep renovation, selling or renting. Other stakeholders show a rather positive perception of the EPC as they are aware of its original goal as a policy instrument to contribute to the energy transition in the building sector. However, admittedly the EPC would not have fulfilled its potential yet.

One of the most obvious common needs among end-users from AT, BE, EL, ES, FI and DE (also partially supported by experts) is the **interest in feedback about real energy consumption**, connected to the need to receive reliable cost indications for running the building and individual recommendations (e.g. realistic investment costs, annual energy savings, information on available subsidies, and links to find appropriate installers, as well as more information about energy-efficient technologies). Likewise, end users from all countries except for FI demanded hints for every-day behaviour to save energy.

REBs members reflected on the main end-users perspective analysis outputs and recommendations during the 2nd round of REB meetings. They were asked for their agreement or dissenting opinions about the presented needs summarized in five categories (see Figure 8.a).

Figure 8.a) REB members' approval rate about end-users' and other stakeholders' needs. b) REB members' approval rate about possible and suggested solutions

In summary, information about the real energy consumption related to the energy costs was an aim for 91% of all participants, even though energy costs vary on the market and over time, and thus cost predictions should be viewed with caution; detailed individual recommendations are needed for reasons of transparency in the renovation market; affordable prices and comparability of the quality of the buildings should remain a focus. The risk of having too much information was highlighted; therefore the EPC could become more modular with different levels of information. Energy audit and environmental certification schemes for the more detailed approach should not be replaced.

3.2.2. Criteria-set for an adequate EPC derived by user need assessment. Possible and suggested solutions

Based on user's needs inputs experts from AT, ES and BE-Flanders suggested **splitting the EPC into two versions**: one user-related version, oriented to end-users, with very visual and simple presentations (e.g. cost savings) and another, more technical version directed to authorities who can use it during decision

making regarding the granting of funds. Besides, it was commonly mentioned to make the EPC more dynamic – which could be realised by connecting the EPC to databases e.g. on fuel costs, policy targets and conversion factors. This would e.g. allow to provide updated information about heating costs to end users. Other than that, as recommended by experts from FI, BE-Flanders and ES, the EPC could become dynamic by making the EPC customizable (dynamic regarding the consideration of different user behaviour). This could be an alternative to providing feedback about real energy consumption. By implication, if the option(s) to make the EPC dynamic were implemented, this would mean that (part of) the EPC would need to become digital in order to display current, updated information.

Even if the needs among different stakeholder differ, a criteria-set for an adequate EPC was developed based on the collected critiques and needs. Hence, an adequate EPC should be **reliable**, **comparable** in the national and international context, **individual** (regarding the building user and climate), **understandable** (also for laymen), **tangible** (for end users because they can refer to real life), **comprehensive** (considering regulative and technical developments), **adequate** and **dynamic & digital**.

Some possible solutions were also discussed between REB members with the purpose of instilling trust and end-user acceptance (see fig 8.b and [13]). They showed a high level of agreement with the benefits of a “digital version of EPC”, as add-on with additional information on consumption data, costs, etc., and improvement of communication between end-users and EPC issues. This last recommendation contrasts with the position of some REB members who think that the EPC should be as self-explaining as possible.

3.3 More understandable EPC report layout. Convergence and prioritization of key indicators

A new layout for EPC report has been proposed in the context of ePANACEA project. Summary sheets templates were designed, initially structured in two parts: administration-oriented and end-users-oriented summary sheets. But finally, general EPC summary sheets for all stakeholders (administration group and end-users group) were adopted plus specific summary sheets for end-users.

The content of each page has been evaluated and discussed in both end-user workshops and REB meetings. Main performance indicators, energy efficiency measures roadmap, additional indicators such as smart readiness indicator (SRI) and conform indicator, etc., have been discussed from the point of view of their pertinence and visualisation.

Overall, the proposed ePANACEA EPC layout was perceived as well structured and very clear and the majority of the REB members and end-users think that target group-oriented summary pages increase usability and user-friendliness of EPC.

However, suggestions for improvement were received from users workshops, focused not only on presentation and visualisation of information, but also on the validity and plausibility of information (e.g. provision of annual energy costs, underlying rating systems of partial performance indicators, valuation basis for recommendations). The greatest need for improvement is regarding the presentation of final energy use disaggregated per energy service and the ratio of renewable and non-renewable energy. In total the message is: the information should be clear, reduced to the necessary and possibly conveyed by means of intuitive illustrations. The EPC should become digital, perhaps also provided as an interactive EPC app. This would facilitate the provision of additional information for interested users.

Regarding main performance indicators there is a strong interest in annual energy costs amongs end-users in all countries, whereas primary energy use is also considered as highly important. However, total primary energy use, non-renewable primary energy use, operationalCO₂eq emissions are preferred by REB members. There is a consensus of disagreement (80%) to use actual conditions for calculating EPC and 46% are totally against to using mainly measured data because it does not provide comparable information about building energy performance.

Overall, indoor air quality and thermal comfort are the most interesting additional indicators for end-users. However, there is a concern between REB members that it may cause new doubts related to EPC (in fact, 44% of them were against to include indicators such as SRI or comfort in the first pages).

In almost all countries information about the total investments required for measures would present the biggest benefit that could motivate participants to pay more for an EPC. 78% of REB members agree with including a roadmap with prioritization and added savings and range of costs of each step.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND POLICY RECOMENDATIONS

An open discussion has been launched within ePANACEA project in order to understand the different needs and expectations of the end-users, EU policy makers and other stakeholders with regards to the next generation of EPCs.

Overall, EPC is perceived by end-users as a standardised document which does not allow to make realistic assumptions about costs for running the building or to obtain specific recommendations. They are interested in receiving feedback about real **energy consumption and energy costs**, connected to obtain reliable information about **individual recommendations** (e.g. realistic investment costs, annual energy savings, information on available subsidies, and links to find appropriate installers, as well as more information about energy-efficient technologies), additional indicators such as comfort or air quality, affordable prices for EPCs, etc.

However, experts consistently point out the original purpose of the EPC – a tool to compare the EE of buildings - which excludes information about the real energy consumption. Besides, experts want to refrain from adding more information to the EPC which is already complex and difficult to understand for end-users.

Additionally, energy costs vary on the market and over time, and thus cost predictions should be viewed with caution; detailed individual recommendations are needed for reasons of transparency in the renovation market; affordable prices and comparability of the quality of the buildings should remain a focus. The risk of having too much information was highlighted; therefore the EPC could become more modular with different levels of information.

ePANACEA proposes a way to integrate the “end-user dimension” (consumption data, actual operational conditions): providing it as supplementary information to the end-users, e.g. on a separate summary sheet. This may increase end-users trust on EPC calculation results and contribute to more robust economic estimation of energy efficiency measures and more realistic tailored recommendations.

Hence, some policy recommendations from ePANACEA project are:

A next generation of features related to input data, covering for instance:

- Improved consideration of user behaviour and occupant patterns.
- Inclusion of smart and novel technologies, such as on-site production of renewable energy and advanced energy management systems.
- Use of building monitoring data to increase accuracy.

A next generation of outcomes that include among others:

- New global and partial indicators better understandable by end users based on actual energy use.
- Recommendations related to user behaviour.
- Tailored recommendations based on cost-optimal solution for deep renovation of buildings (or a series of them –a roadmap-, investment costs, etc.)
 - Double oriented information included in the EPC (on the one hand focused on Administration needs based on standardized operational conditions and on the other hand focused on building users' needs based on actual use) or supplementary end-user-oriented information.

A next generation of tools:

- Next generation of EPCs needs a next generation of web based tools and their innovative capabilities, taking advantage of power computing on cloud.
- ePANACEA suggestion integrates inverse modelling and automated calibration procedures for dynamic Building Energy Simulation. This enables obtaining a calibrated model based on actual consumption patterns at the same time that will provide a more accurate standard EPC after correction by climate and use.

Other recommendations for the implementation of EPC as a policy tool, e.g.:

- Registration of EPCs should be mandatory and there should be central institutions where the EPCs are registered.
- Site visits should be mandatory when issuing an EPC.
- Requirements to issue an EPC should become more precise and demanding so that less experts are allowed to issue an EPC. EPC certifiers should receive regular training.
- The communication about the EPC to end-users should be improved by intermediaries (certifiers, assessors, building companies, selling agencies and town councils).
- Pursue the idea to make the EPC digital. This would have the advantage that additional information could easily be accessed by interested end-users and that the information could be updated ("dynamic EPC -consumption data, costs, etc-) or connected with updated databases (e.g. measures, investment costs, energy costs, conversion factors...).
- Provide partial indicators e.g. for walls, floor, roof, doors and windows to make it comprehensible where the weak points of the building are.
- Include additional indicators: indoor air quality, thermal comfort, smart readiness of the building, the fraction of RES production for statistical purpose and national energy policy.
- Use benchmarking for final energy use and CO₂ emissions (importance of the reference).
- Streamline the content of the EPC for end users: do not make the EPC more complex, reduce the content for end users, additional information should be covered in an additional document/tool. The EPC for end users could be simplified by graphic representations, clear and short messages.

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